

Ben Sira 36:1-22

Expert source: Benjamin Wright, Lehigh University

Data source: Prayer in the Ancient World

Entered by Brandon Brown, Baylor University

** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Early Rabbinism, Semitic, Late Second Temple Judaism, Religious Group, Prayer, Text, Hebrewic, Ancient Hebrew, West Semitic, Language, Canaanite, Northwest Semitic, Afro-Asiatic, Jewish Traditions, Central Semitic, Ancient Greek text, Early Jewish Literature, Greek

This text is a selection from the book of Ben Sira, a collection of proverbs and teachings written by a Jewish sage in Hebrew in the 2nd century BCE and later translated into Greek (likely in Alexandria) by an author claiming to be his grandson. Ben Sira participates in the Near Eastern tradition of wisdom literature, drawing its most direct inspiration from the book of Proverbs. Over time, Ben Sira became familiar within the rabbinic Jewish community – it is cited by the Talmud on multiple occasions – and has been included in some versions of the Christian Bible as either “Sirach” or “Ecclesiasticus” (its Latin name). Though the Book of Ben Sira was not canonized within the Jewish tradition, there are resonances to the text in Jewish literature in the late antique and medieval periods. The oldest preserved versions of Ben Sira are in Hebrew, Greek, Latin, and Syriac. Though they bear the same message, some slight differences exist in the translations. Six medieval manuscripts were found in the Cairo Genizah in 1896, and more fragmentary ancient copies dating to 50-70 BCE were found at the Dead Sea. This selection is a prayer of petition to God to deliver Israel and bring misfortune to its enemies. It is written in poetic form and interweaves praise of the nature and power of God with petitions for his aid for the Jewish people.

Date Range: 200 BCE - 100 CE

Region: Jerusalem

Region tags: Israel, Palestine, Middle East, Qumran, Israel in the Second Temple period

Jerusalem and/or Alexandria

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Wright, Benjamin G. III. “Ben Sira 36:1-22.” In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://brill.com/display/serial/PAMW?language=en>

Notes: Wright, Benjamin G. III. "Ben Sira 36:1–22." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.bensira.org/>

– Source 1 Description: Digital photographs of the extant Hebrew portions of the Book of Ben Sira

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Leather

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

– Paper

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Tomb

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Cemetery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Temple

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Shrine

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Altar

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Church

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Mosque

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Synagogue

– Yes

Notes: The medieval manuscripts come from the Cairo Genizah.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Monument

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

Notes: Fragments were found among the Dead Sea Scrolls. Other manuscripts were found at Masada and in the Medieval Cairo Genizah

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Hilltops

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Copies of the Hebrew text of Ben Sira were found among the Dead Sea documents as well as in the Cairo Genizah.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Specify

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The book of Ben Sira is considered early Jewish literature, but did not become part of the canon of the Hebrew Bible. In its translations, it became part of some Christian canons of scripture.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: The text was originally written in Hebrew, and later translated into Greek (and later Syriac and Latin).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: Some Early Jewish texts, such as Jubilees, argue for the sacred status of Hebrew. Ben Sira does not.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The text is a selection from the Book of Ben Sira, or the Sirach, a book of wisdom literature written during the mid Second Temple period of Judaism.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: This selection from the Book of Ben Sira and the Book itself are wisdom literature - akin to the book of Proverbs in the biblical canon, written to praise the Jewish God, ask for his blessings upon Israel, and to discuss the worthy life within the Jewish community, all in ways reflective of Jewish culture.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: No. The text is itself a prayer of petition to the Jewish God that he deliver those of the nation of Israel and bring misfortune among its enemies.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: The referenced God, according to the Jewish tradition, is in a covenant to bless and protect the people of Israel as his chosen people.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: The supreme high god possesses all features traditionally associated with the Jewish God.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The Jewish God referenced here is omniscient, meaning that he possesses all knowledge.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: The supreme high god possesses all features traditionally associated with the Jewish God.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

In trance possession

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Through divination practices

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Only through religious specialists

– No

Notes: Religious specialists in the Jewish tradition may aid the communication with and understanding of the Jewish God, but they are not the only source of communication with it/him.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Other form of communication with living

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text makes petitions and praise to the Jewish God.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/ as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Notes: Not in this prayer text, but expectation of ritual offerings is attested elsewhere in Ben Sira (Sir 14:11; 35:9; 38:11; 45:16; 46:16; 50:12-15)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Notes: The prayer does not mention murder, but requests divine help and vengeance against foreign enemies in general terms, without specifying the nature of the threat to Israel. Elsewhere in Ben Sira, murder is a concern (Sir 9:13; 34:26).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: Not mentioned in this prayer, but sex is a concern elsewhere in Ben Sira (Sir 41:17)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: This might be inferred from the request that prophets be found trustworthy (36:21)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

Notes: Oaths are not mentioned in this prayer text, but elsewhere Ben Sira does portray oath breaking as sin (Sir 23:11).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

Notes: Not mentioned in this prayer, but respect for elders is expressed elsewhere in Ben Sira

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

Notes: Gossiping is not mentioned in this prayer, but gossiping is a concern elsewhere in Ben Sira (Sir 19:6, 12)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

Notes: Property crimes are not explicitly mentioned in this prayer, but may be implied in the general reference to "those who harm your people" etc. It is a topic of concern elsewhere in Ben Sira (Sir 41:19).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– No

Notes: Not in this prayer, but elsewhere in Ben Sira (Sir 35:15; 38:11; 50:1-21)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: Not mentioned explicitly in this prayer but implied by petition for God to fill the temple

with his glory (36:19); ritual performance is a concern elsewhere in Ben Sira, and especially his description of the high priest's ritual performance in Sir 50.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

Notes: Not in this prayer, but economic fairness and justice are concerns elsewhere in Ben Sira (e.g., Sir 42:2-4).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: In this prayer, Ben Sira asks the Jewish God to repeat on Israel's enemies the kinds of acts that God wrought against Egypt in the Exodus.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Notes: Not in this prayer, where punishment is through divine agency, but elsewhere in Ben Sira punishment can also be by natural cause-effect consequences.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

Notes: In this prayer, punishment is just directed toward enemies. Elsewhere in Ben Sira the motif of punishment as discipline to inculcate proper behavior is prominent (e.g., Sir 18:14).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: The punishment described within the text is directed at those who have been hostile to the people of Israel, and is described as humbling, scattering, or pouring out the wrath of the Jewish God on these people.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

Notes: Not as they are described in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that this is a major topic of this text, yes, deliverance from those hostile to the Israelites often is naturally associated with punishing or ruining the plans of their captors.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

Notes: Not explicitly mentioned in this text, but probably implied as one possible source of disaster on enemies.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Notes: This could be the case, but is not explicitly mentioned within the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ **Sickness or illness?**

– Yes

Notes: This could be the case, but is not explicitly mentioned within the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ **Impaired reproduction?**

– Yes

Notes: This could be the case, but is not explicitly mentioned within the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ **Back luck visited on descendants?**

– No

Notes: Not mentioned in this text, but could be implied.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Other?**

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the rewarding of the petitions described in the text honors the covenant that the people of Israel are delivered from hardship by their God, yes, the reward would, in effect, encourage and enforce adherence to the Jewish religion.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

Notes: The rewards described in this text, which may be summarily described as delivering the people of Israel from hardship in accordance with their covenant with God, are the main focus of the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

Notes: This may be the case elsewhere, but this is not a reward described in this text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

Notes: As in "Gather all the tribes of Jacob" (36:13)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Notes: Not in this particular text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– No

Notes: Not in this particular text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

Notes: Not in this particular text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Other?

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Much of the tone of the text is eschatological, but does not refer to a specific eschaton and/or its features.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
Status of Readership:

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Establishment of new political system

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– I don't know

Notes: This does not apply, as the eschaton is not described explicitly here.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Courage (in battle)**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Courage (generic)**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Generosity/charity**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Selflessness/selfless giving**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Righteousness/moral rectitude**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ **Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Ben Sira discusses children and their obligations to father and mother.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Cooperation

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership:

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Status of Readership: ✓ Elite

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: In several passages Ben Sira encourages offering proper sacrifices (e.g., 7:31).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership:

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period
Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Scribes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership:

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Ben Sira refers to his own school, his beth midrash.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: However, most literate individuals would have been male during the Second Temple period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: However, most literate individuals would have been male during the Second Temple period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Toward the end of the book, Ben Sira encourages students to study in his school and they will "acquire silver and gold" (51:28).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: However, the text does mention the Temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 180 BCE - 132 CE

Region: Jewish settlement in the land of Israel at the Second Temple period

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Ben Sira 36:1-22, Gilbert, Maurice. "Prayer in the Book of Ben Sira. Function and Relevance". In *Deuterocanonical and Cognate Literature Yearbook 2004: Prayer from Tobit to Qumran*, edited by Renate Egger-Wenzel and Jeremy Corley, 117-35. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2004.

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Reference: Ben Sira 36:1-22, Ziegler, Joseph. *Septuaginta. Vetus Testamentum Graecum Auctoritate Academiae Scientiarum Gottingensis Editum XII/2. Sapientia Iesu Filii Sirach*. 2nd ed.. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1980.